

EDUCATION OF THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF A BOXER

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ABSTRACT

This article describes in detail the characteristics of physical training of young boxers, and mainly analyzes the practical importance of training the physical quality of strength.

KEYWORDS

Boxing, strength physical quality, physical training, competition stage, preparation stage, physical qualities

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье подробно описаны особенности физической подготовки юных боксеров, а в основном проанализировано практическое значение тренировки физических качеств силы.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Бокс, силовые физические качества, физическая подготовка, соревновательный этап, этап подготовки, физические качества.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada yosh bokschilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligining xususiyatlari batafsil yoritib berilgan va asosan kuchning jismoniy sifatlarini tayyorlashning amaliy ahamiyati tahlil qilingan.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Boks, kuchli jismoniy sifatlar, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, musobaqa bosqichi, tayyorgarlik bosqichi, jismoniy sifatlar.

Physical training is the basis for achieving high results in boxing. Without good physical fitness in the conditions of a duel, it is impossible to effectively and long-term manifestation of the technical, tactical and mental skills and qualities of a boxer. Therefore, physical training in unity with the process of improving the elements of a boxer's technique and tactics is one of the leading ones in the training as a whole.

The main physical qualities of each athlete include: strength, speed, agility and endurance. These qualities are important in any sport, but in each sport they manifest themselves specifically, under the influence of the characteristics of its technique and tactics.

The conditions and nature of the efforts developed during the fight are different, which determines the diverse manifestation of strength in boxing.

The dynamic power of a boxer is manifested in movement, i.e. in the so-called dynamic mode. This, for example, is the strength developed in strikes, defenses, movements, etc.

According to the nature of the efforts, the dynamic force in boxing is divided into explosive, fast and slow.

Explosive force refers to the manifestation of force with maximum acceleration. Such strength, for example, develops in the accented blows of a boxer.

Fast force is manifested in movements in which the speed of movement plays a predominant role, and relatively small inert resistances are inherent in it.

Slow force is manifested in relatively slow movements performed with little or no acceleration. A typical case of the manifestation of slow power in boxing is the direct forceful overcoming of the opponent's resistance in close combat at the moment of captures, holding, etc.

Different modes of operation and fighting styles of boxers require a variety of manifestations of strength, especially when they perform striking actions.

So, a boxer - "tempo" needs a force that allows him to inflict a series of rapidly alternating relatively weak blows, overcoming his inertial efforts and the opponent's resistance.

In a boxer - "knockout", on the contrary, the main feature is the ability to inflict a strong, accentuated blow with maximum or near-limit force of an "explosive" nature.

The manifestation of slow strength, especially in direct contact with the enemy at the time of the power struggle and the physical "suppression" of the enemy, is characteristic of a boxer - a "silovik".

A boxer - "player" assumes a protective position before and after delivering a blow, and therefore he has a reduced ability to deliver the most powerful blow. He achieves the effect in percussion actions due to fast and accurate strikes with the development of an "explosive" impulse at the beginning of the strike.

Since the nature of the manifestation of strength in boxing is different (explosive, fast, slow strength), in practice, the athlete must use the appropriate means and methods to develop each type of strength, focusing on those that correspond to his individual style.

The education of the strength of a boxer should go in two directions.

1. Widespread use of general developmental strength exercises on gymnastic apparatus and without them, exercises with weights, in resistance with a partner, etc.

2. Education of strength by means of special preparatory and special exercises. These include exercises in the direct overcoming of the opponent's resistance in the form of repulsion ("push-push" wrestling), elements of the opponent's force retention, wrestling, etc., overcoming the inertia of one's own body during defenses and during the transition from defenses to strikes and vice versa ; education of impact force on bags, paws, paired with an opponent, etc.

To develop the ability of the main muscles of a boxer to quickly (instantly) develop efforts, up to maximum, throwing and pushing stones, cores, stuffed balls of

different weights, exercises with dumbbells, expanders, work with an ax, shovel, hammer, exercises with a barbell and others

There are two methods of developing the strength of a boxer, analytical and holistic.

The holistic method is fundamental in developing the special strength of a boxer. It is characterized by the simultaneous improvement of both the basic power capabilities of the boxer and his special skills.

Among the exercises aimed at improving the boxer's special strength by a holistic method within the framework of the mastered skill are special preparatory and special exercises with weights (lead weights, light weight dumbbells, etc.): "shadow boxing", exercises on bags, paws and other shells, complicated performance of simulation exercises in water, etc.

The analytical method of exercises allows you to selectively bring up the strength of individual muscle groups that carry the main load. For example, an effective means of cultivating the strength of the muscles - the extensor arm, which do not carry the main load during impacts, are speed-strength exercises with weights of various weights (dumbbells, stuffed balls, etc.), gymnastic exercises in fast push-ups in emphasis, jerk and jerk exercises with a barbell, power blocks, etc.

The most "effective means of educating explosive and fast strength in a boxer, both holistically and analytically, are exercises with optimal weights, which should be performed with the maximum possible acceleration. The boxer must select the amount of weight, taking into account the weight category and the level of his preparedness. When cultivating strength with with the help of exercises with weights, the boxer should repeat the task until the speed of movement begins to noticeably decrease, the structure of movement is not disturbed. After that, the boxer needs to do exercises for relaxation and active stretching of the muscles involved in the previous movement. Then repeatedly repeat the same movements with maximum speed and

structural accuracy characteristic of a special movement, using the effect of force consequences..

Distinguish between general and special speed of an athlete. General speed is the ability to display speed in a wide variety of movements, for example, in sprinting, sports games, etc. General speed is manifested in the rapid start of movement, the speed of the athlete's non-specific movement, the rapid execution of single and frequent movements, the ability to instantly switch from one movement to another. The boxer's special speed is manifested in the latent reaction time, the time of one punch, the maximum rate of a series of punches, and the speed of movement. A close relationship between general and special speed is usually manifested in junior level athletes in the early stages of their sports development. With the growth of sportsmanship and qualifications of an athlete, the level of fitness from general developmental exercises to special ones decreases.

For rational training of speed qualities of a boxer, the circular method is the most effective. After the warm-up, the athletes are divided into four subgroups. Each of the subgroups of boxers, on the instructions of the coach, occupies a certain "station". Each "station" is designed to improve a specific speed, quality.

Usually, at the 1st "station" boxers improve the speed of single blows, at the 2nd - the speed of defensive reactions, at the 3rd - the speed of movement and at the 4th - the speed of serial blows performed with the maximum possible frequency.

To preserve the stereotype of time intervals that are typical for competitive combat, the time for performing exercises at "stations" should be one round, i.e. 3 minutes.

In boxing, in order to improve the overall endurance of an athlete, general preparatory exercises (cross-country running, swimming, skiing, sports games, etc.) and special exercises (freestyle and conditional fights, work in pairs, on shells, etc.) are used.

To achieve a high level of endurance, a certain system for choosing exercises and their organization is necessary. Experimental studies have shown that a boxer's overall endurance improves when specific exercises are used in training that cause the greatest energy shifts and are performed at a significant "pulse value" of approximately 180 bpm. (sparring, freestyle and conditional fights, work in pairs to improve technical and tactical skills, bag work). An effective means of increasing endurance in training is to increase the round to 5 minutes or more.

To improve special endurance, which is manifested in the boxer's ability to perform intense work of maximum power, special and specially preparatory exercises are mainly used (sparring, conditional and freestyle fights, exercises on shells, "shadow boxing", exercises with a partner in pairs without gloves, with stuffed balls, in movements, etc.).

The main way to improve special endurance by selecting special training exercises is to intensify the boxer's activity in exercises in freestyle and conditional fights (due to frequent change of partners, close combat, increase, difficulty of tasks, etc.), in exercises with a bag, the boxer performs with maximum speed and intensity during one round 10 - 15 explosive short series (lasting from 1 to 1.5 s each), and in the intervals between series (10 -15 s) - actions at a calm pace. This is followed by a rest of 1.5 - 2 minutes, after which the boxer again performs an exercise with a bag (3 rounds in total),

To improve the other side of endurance, exercises are used during which continuous intensive work (hitting the bag, paws, pear for 20–30 s) alternates with work at a slow pace (for 40–60 s).

When educating the endurance of boxers, correct breathing is of great importance. The boxer's breathing must be continuous and deep enough. It has been found that the breath mode with emphasis on the breath during strong blows is the most effective. This contributes not only to better ventilation of the lungs, but also increases the force of blows. When delivering serial blows, boxers must breathe continuously, however,

each blow should not be accompanied by a sharp exhalation, which must end either the entire series of blows or a single accented blow.

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